

Biosynthesis and Metabolism of Anthraquinone Derivatives

Authors : Dmitry Yu. Korulkin, Raissa A. Muzychkina

Abstract : In review the generalized data about biosynthetic routes formation anthraquinone molecules in natural cells. The basic possibilities of various ways of biosynthesis of different quinoid substances are shown.

Keywords : anthraquinones, biochemical evolution, biosynthesis, metabolism

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